

ISic3507

I.Sicily inscription 3507

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

prayer

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)****Provenance**

in a dry stone wall in cava Ritiddini, territory of Rosolini, c.12km
from Modica

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Rosolini, cava Ritiddini, in a dry stone wall, c.12km from Modica

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336687

1. Κ(ύρι) ε βοήτι
2. τῆς ὑκ[ίας²⁶οίκίας²⁶ — —]
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491423

EDCS 46600164

PHI 336687

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2007.0676

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 57.0884

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 51.1381

Manganaro, G. 2001. Byzantina Siciliae. *Minima Epigraphica et Papyrologica.* 4: 131-178. At 142-146 fig.7-10

Sammito, A.M., Rizzone, V.G. 2007. Aspetti della cristianizzazione negli Ibeli sud-orientali. In Bonacasa Carra, R.M., Vitale, E.(eds.), *La cristianizzazione in Italia fra tardoantico e altomedioevo.* Palermo. pp. 1613-1646. At 1625-1626

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3507. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388688>